

Evaluating P-Possum As Risk Prediction Tool In Emergency Laparotomy In Tertiary Care Hospital

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: September 04, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 06, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Evaluating P-Possum, patients' physiological, Civil Hospital Karachi's</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6419883</p>	<p>Background: The patients' physiological state, morbidity rates following emergency laparotomies can be misleading. There are a number of surgical risk assessments that are widely used, including the Portsmouth-POSSUM (P-POSSUM), a version of the physiologic and operational severity score that is used to count the number of deaths during surgery. These facts are frequently acquired from the operation room itself.</p> <p>Objective: The purpose of this study is to investigate the predictive efficacy of the P-POSSUM scores in patients receiving emergency laparotomy.</p> <p>Methodology: Civil Hospital Karachi's emergency department patients were the subjects of a cross-sectional, qualitative, prospective study. Our target enrollment is 90 patients during the course of the research. People who come from the hospital's emergency room will be included in the study. A Google form will be filled out for each patient with their demographics and the type of admission, ASA grade, urgency of surgery, P-POSSUM score, indication of surgery, length of stay and outcome cardiac signs (GCS, GCS, Cardiac Status Hb, WBC, operative parameters), operative blood loss, peritoneal examination, malignancy status, physiology score, operative severity and morbidity calculator and mortality measures.</p> <p>Results: The average age of the study's 100 participants was 44.37 years with 16.541 Std. P-POSSUM projected a morbidity mean of 43.82 with 31.8 Std, but P-POSSUM predicted a mortality mean of 10.37 with 16.89 Std. Chi-square tests revealed considerable link between observed and anticipated mortality, with P values of 0.003 for P- POSSUM indicating meaningful association. Whereas, anticipated morbidity value which significantly overestimates actual morbidity. There is no correlation between P-POSSUM's overestimation of morbidity and a P value of 0.521 in a correlation test.</p> <p>Conclusion: P-POSSUM appear to be good and valid markers for use in the risk prediction of morbidity and mortality in the Pakistani population</p>

Introduction

Emergency laparotomy comprises multiple surgeries done on diverse group of high risk patients making preoperative assessment exceedingly difficult assignment for surgeons [1]. It is vital that patients are evaluated with a comprehensive approach so as to predict the mortality and efforts made to decrease the risk [2]. Portsmouth-Physiological and Operative Severity Score is one of the rating methods frequently used to forecast the hazards. It enumerates the Mortality and Morbidity in high risk patients [3]. Operations done in emergency comprise of a distinct group of patients receiving significant procedures for both traumatic and non-traumatic indications [4]. They are unwittingly at excessive risk of morbidity. Even in industrialised countries the rate are as high as 10 percent and 18 percent in 30 day period.

A study conducted in UK across 27 hospitals finds between 3 percent and 45 percent. These data are much higher than the death rates for elective surgical operations even for difficult procedures [5,6]. It has been always been surgeons priority to discover risk factors for minimising morbidity and death after emergency laparotomy to enhance outcomes [7,8]. Numerous scoring systems have been used for this purpose, including the POSSUM (Physiological and Operative Severity Score for the Enumeration of Mortality and Morbidity) and its modified version P-POSSUM (Portsmouth - POSSUM), the SRS (Surgical Risk Scale), the PMP (Pre-operative Mortality Predictor), the ASA (American Society of Anesthesiology) classification, the National Emergency Laparotomy Audit (NELA) risk model [9]. The aim is to create or include a technology that assists in identifying high-risk patients in order to provide differentiated perioperative care and improve results [10].

While identifying high-risk patients requires routine risk assessment, the Portsmouth-Physiological and Operative Severity Score for Mortality and Morbidity enumeration (P-POSSUM) has been used to predict mortality in patients undergoing various types of surgery. P-POSSUM has been used to predict outcomes in

neurosurgery [11], gastric cancer patients [12], critical care patients [13], and patients having emergency surgery [14]. However, its predictive value varies according to clinical context. Several research have examined the efficacy of P-POSSUM scoring to predict mortality risk following surgery in the elderly, and they indicate that while P-POSSUM scoring may be a viable predictor with moderate discrimination, its relative value in excluding remains unknown [14]. Choosing a compatible Risk assessment tools can be used to supplement clinical judgments in selecting acceptable treatment plans, informing consent, and personalizing perioperative care. They can also be used for risk adjustment, thereby assisting in quality improvement.

Rationale: The purpose of this study is to determine the applicability and convenience of use of P-Possum as a predictor of morbidity and death in patients having emergency laparotomy in a public sector hospital.

METHODOLOGY

This is a cross-sectional prospective qualitative research of patients admitted to Civil Hospital Karachi's emergency department. 90 patients have been evaluated during the study period by using a 10% observed mortality rate (Thirunavukkarasu S et al. 2018, with a 95% confidence limit and 5% precision. We have continued collecting data until we reach the required sample size. Patients were enrolled in the study from the emergency department. Google forms were used to enter the particular parameters for each patient. Patients undergoing emergency laprotomy were admitted to the hospital for the duration of their stay. Patients were enrolled in the study from the emergency department. Specific parameters for each patient were entered into Google forms, including demographic information, type of admission, ASA grade, surgical urgency, P-POSSUM score, indication for surgery, length of stay, and outcome cardiac signs, GCS, Cardiac Status Hb, WBC, operative parameters, operative blood loss, peritoneal examination malignancy status, and physiology score (according to risk calculator), Operative severity, risk calculator-adjusted morbidity, death outcomes, and discharge status. The patient were followed up until the end of his or her hospital stay, and a P-possum prediction was made using the guideline. Apart from demographic data, projected and observed morbidity, death, and pre-discharge events were collected.

Statistical Analysis:

Following data collection, the data will be entered into Excel for preliminary sorting and cleaning before being exported to SPSS for final analysis. The quantitative variables will be expressed in terms of mean and standard deviation (SD), whereas the qualitative variables will be expressed in terms of frequency and percentages. The independent sample t-test or Mann-Whitney U test will be used to assess quantitative data, while the chi square test will be used to analyse qualitative variables. Chi-square tests were used to determine the P-value for categorical variables. A p value <0.05 is deemed significant.

RESULTS

The study's 100 participants had an average age of 44.37 years and a standard deviation of 16.541 (table 1). The demographic continuous variables were recorded and evaluated as listed in table 1 and 2. P-POSSUM predicted a morbidity mean of 43.82 with 31.8 standard deviation, but a mortality mean of 10.37 with 16.89 standard deviation. Chi-square tests found a significant link between observed and expected mortality, with P values of 0.003 for P- POSSUM indicating a significant relationship. Expected morbidity value, on the other hand, vastly overestimates actual morbidity. There is no link between POSSUM's overestimation of morbidity and a correlation test P value of 0.521. Table 3 and 4.

Table 1:

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age (years)	90	20	70	44.37	16.541
Systolic BP	90	80	160	115.27	19.402
Pulse rate/min	90	76	135	96.18	13.661
Glasgow comma score	90	9	15	14.10	1.424
Hemoglobin	90	5.0	58.0	14.166	10.3103
White blood cells	90	6000.0	26600.0	13357.844	6479.2385
Blood urea	90	.5	88.0	18.490	22.2884

Serum Na	90	129.00	150.00	136.2667	5.38162
Serum K	90	.0	4.8	2.814	1.6302
Operation blood loss	90	50	2000	279.11	305.175

Table 2:

Variables	Frequency	%
Gender		
Males	61	67.8
Females	29	32.2
Age Groups		
>60 years	22	75.6
<60 years	68	24.4
Cardiac Signs		
Normal	79	87.8
Raised JVP	5	5.6
Borderline cardiomegaly	6	6.7
Respiratory Signs		
No dyspnea	75	83.3
Dyspnea on exertion	7	7.8
Dyspnea at rest	8	8.9
Operation Type		
Minor	18	20.0
Moderate	59	65.6
Major	13	14.4
No. of Procedures		
1	86	95.6
2	4	4.4
Peritoneal Contamination		
No soiling	48	53.3
Minor soiling	24	26.7
Local pus	6	6.7
Free bowel/pus/blood	12	13.3
Malignancy		
No malignancy	61	67.8
Primary malignancy	29	32.2
CEPOD		
Elective	18	20.0
Urgent	67	74.4
Emergency	5	5.6

Table 3:

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Physiological score	90	12	37	22.36	8.812
Operative severity score	90	6.0	30.0	11.420	5.8879
Morbidity prediction	90	5.5	97.9	43.823	31.8593

Mortality prediction	90	.2	65.7	10.374	16.8913
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Table 4:

Variables	Frequency	%	P Value
Outcome			
Discharged without event	54	60.0	0.632
Still hospitalized with morbidity	23	25.6	0.521
Death	13	14.4	0.003
Cardiac Signs			
Normal	82	91.1	0.044
Cardiac Abnormality	8	8.9	
Respiratory Signs			
Normal	72	80.0	0.031
Dyspnea	18	20.0	

DISCUSSION:

Medical treatment has traditionally aimed to offer the best care available to patients in order to minimise the likelihood of adverse effects. We can measure the quality of patient care and develop fresh treatment strategies by comparing the success and failure rates of various treatment modalities. The overall health of a patient or the illness process for which surgery was performed may not be sufficient to compare fatality rates appropriately. POSSUM created a risk-adjusted scoring technique to address this issue. Despite the fact that P-POSSUM, a modified version of POSSUM, has been marketed as a more accurate scoring system[7,9], P-POSSUM cannot be beneficial unless it is linked to the overall health of the local population. [3]. This is especially true for patients in countries like Pakistan, where malnutrition is widespread and often goes unrecognised until it is too late. [12,13]

When comparing surgical outcomes, the patient population must be considered. P-POSSUM is a surgical audit instrument designed to assess the quality of surgical care. [3] To compare audits of different patient groups, it is necessary to take into account the patients' physiological status and the level of surgical intervention. The POSSUM equation was revised for the P-POSSUM mortality prediction equation. Comparing observed and expected mortality rates for persons at low risk became easier when the P-POSSUM equation was used rather than exponential analysis. [6]

In 90 evaluated patients, the actual death and morbidity rates were compared to those predicted by POSSUM and P-POSSUM. Between April and December of last year, the general surgery department performed 90 emergency laparotomies on patients admitted to the general surgery department. In comparison to Aggarwal et al., Jones et al., and Bhalsod et al., the study had 120, 117, and 118 individuals, respectively. [13,14,15] Men outnumbered women 61 to 29, resulting in a male to female ratio of 2:1. Anbarasu et al. discovered a 2.3:1 ratio in their investigation. As Anbarasu et al. discovered, 85.0 percent of patients were under the age of 60 and the median age was 40.0 years (range, 18–86 years) (87.5 percent). There were 41 peptic perforations, six small intestine perforations, one appendicular perforation, and 24 intestinal blockages necessitating an emergency laparotomy (8 cases).

In poor countries, appendicitis-related emergency laparotomies account for 29.1 percent of all emergency laparotomies. Additionally, the 30-day mortality rate, physiological and surgical parameters, as well as other critical data, were collected. These methods were used to calculate the risk of mortality and morbidity for each patient. The risk categories of patients were classified according to their observed and predicted mortality. The forecast's accuracy was determined using chi-squared analysis. P-POSSUM projected a morbidity mean of 43.82 with 31.8 Std, but P-POSSUM predicted a mortality mean of 10.37 with 16.89 Std. Chi-square tests revealed considerable link between observed and anticipated mortality, with P values of 0.003 for P- POSSUM indicating meaningful association. Whereas, anticipated morbidity value which significantly overestimates actual morbidity.

In a previous study, POSSUM and P-POSSUM had O:E ratios of 0.29 when linear regression analysis was used. There are P-POSSUM values of 0.66 and a POSSUM value of 0.39 in Aggarwal and Columbus et al [6,13]. Furthermore, 0.18 and 0.35-0 are available. As in prior research such as those of Aggarwal et al., there was no statistically significant difference between observed and projected mortality rates, as determined by POSSUM (2 = 2.1; degree of freedom = 3; P = 0.55). Aggarwal et al.[13] and Paul et al.[16] observed comparable values: is 0.148 and P-POSSUM (2 = 1.23, degree of freedom = 3, P = 0.85), respectively, are 0.619 and 0.17. [16] As illustrated, both the observed and expected morbidity P-POSSUMS exceeded 70. When the degree of freedom

was set to six, the projected and observed mortality rates were not statistically different (O:E ratio of 0.87, P = 0.75).

In our analysis, the P-POSSUM chi square tests were revealed to be significant predictors of surgical outcomes. One of these equations can be used to correctly predict patients' post-operative recovery. Mortality and morbidity are not the only factors to examine in this method. The study discovered a correlation between surgical morbidity and outcome.

Morbidity-predicting markers, such as POSSUM, have a bigger effect on patients who are at a higher risk of morbidity than on those who are at a lower risk. On the contrary, P-POSSUM properly predicted death in groups at high risk while somewhat underestimating it in groups at low risk. According to P-POSSUM, the mortality equation predicted death accurately on an aggregate level, and hence may be utilised with confidence. POSSUM and P-POSSUM were significant risk factors for morbidity and mortality in patients undergoing emergency laparotomies. According to Thahir et al., P-POSSUM did not reliably predict death in neurosurgical patients. [17]

CONCLUSION

P-POSSUM appear to be excellent indicators for predicting mortality and to some extent, morbidity in Pakistani population (surgical outcome). These diagnostics assist high-risk individuals more than low-risk ones.

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